

Fisher Statistics Should Progress To Quantum Language

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Recently, I proposed the concept of quantum language. This can be characterized as a kind of linguistic turn of quantum mechanics, the true Copenhagen interpretation and a scientific foundation for philosophical epistemology. In this paper I propose that Fisher statistics should progress to quantum language with the concept of measurement (i.e., observable, POVM). Otherwise, statistics risks being viewed merely as a subset of applied mathematics. The present formulation does not aim to conform to contemporary pedagogy or philosophical trends. However, I am convinced that in 10 years, AI will choose quantum language as the foundation of statistics.

1 Introduction: the true Copenhagen interpretation

As seen in Figure 1 below, I propose that quantum language (= QL) is the scientific ultimate goal of epistemology (*cf.* ref. [13]). In this paper, I introduce “commutative C*-QL” located in ⑩ in Figure 1 below as an evolution of Fisher statistics ⑦.

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QM is standard quantum mechanics (i.e., von Neumann's quantum mechanics), formulated in Hilbert space H (or precisely, $B(H)$, all bounded linear operators on H) as follows (*cf.* ref. [3]):

$$\boxed{\text{QM}} = \underbrace{\boxed{\text{measurement}}}_{\text{Born}}^{[\text{Axiom}^{\text{QM}} 1]} + \underbrace{\boxed{\text{equation of motion}}}_{\text{the Schrödinger equation}}^{[\text{Axiom}^{\text{QM}} 2]} + \left[\text{CI (=Copenhagen interpretation)} \right]^{[\text{the manual to use Axioms}^{\text{QM}} 1 \text{ and } 2]} \text{ (in } B(H)) \quad (1)$$

This is naturally recognized as a kind of physics (metaphysics); nevertheless, it has an epistemic aspect. However, it is noteworthy that Axiom 1 (measurement) implies the existence of a measurer, suggesting that QM also has an epistemological aspect.

On the other hand, QL (*cf.* refs. [11, 12]) is formulated in a subalgebra $\mathcal{A}(\subseteq B(H))$ as follows:

$$\boxed{\text{QL}} = \underbrace{\boxed{\text{measurement}}}_{\text{Born}}^{[\text{Axiom}^{\text{QL}} 1]} + \underbrace{\boxed{\text{causal relation}}}_{\text{the Schrödinger equation}}^{[\text{Axiom}^{\text{QL}} 2]} + \left[\text{linguistic CI} \right]^{[\text{the manual to use Axioms}^{\text{QL}} 1 \text{ and } 2]} \text{ (in } \mathcal{A})^2 \quad (2)$$

Only one measurement is allowed

This is a mathematical extension of QM, so it is not metaphysics but epistemology. Here, when \mathcal{A} is commutative, QL (i.e., commutative quantum language) is similar to statistics.

If QL is positioned as the scientific culmination of Western philosophical history, then looking back from QL should bring new perspectives to philosophy as a whole (See ref. [18]).

Further, when $\mathcal{A}_c(\subseteq \mathcal{A} \subseteq B(H))$ is commutative, we get the commutative quantum language such as

$$\boxed{\text{commutative QL}} = \underbrace{\boxed{\text{measurement}}}_{\text{Born}}^{[\text{Axiom}^{\text{CQL}} 1]} + \underbrace{\boxed{\text{causal relation}}}_{\text{the Schrödinger equation}}^{[\text{Axiom}^{\text{CQL}} 2]} + \left[\text{linguistic CI} \right]^{[\text{the manual to use Axioms}^{\text{QL}} 1 \text{ and } 2]} \text{ (in } \mathcal{A}_c) \quad (3)$$

Only one measurement is allowed

which is further classified as follows (**CC*-QL=commutative C*-QL**, **CW*-QL= commutative W*-QL**):

$$(3) \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \boxed{\text{Commutative C}^*\text{-QL}} = \underbrace{\boxed{\text{measurement}}}_{\text{Sec. 2.2}}^{[\text{Axiom}^{\text{CC}^*\text{QL}} 1]} + \underbrace{\boxed{\text{causal relation}}}_{\text{Sec. 2.4}}^{[\text{Axiom}^{\text{CC}^*\text{QL}};2]} + \left[\text{linguistic CI} \right]^{[\text{the manual to use Axioms}^{\text{QL}} 1 \text{ and } 2]} \text{ (in } \mathcal{A}_{\text{CC}^*}) \\ \approx \boxed{\text{Fisher statistics}} \quad (4) \\ \boxed{\text{Commutative W}^*\text{-QL}} = \underbrace{\boxed{\text{measurement}}}_{\text{Born}}^{[\text{Axiom}^{\text{CW}^*\text{QL}} 1]} + \underbrace{\boxed{\text{causal relation}}}_{\text{the Schrödinger equation}}^{[\text{Axiom}^{\text{CW}^*\text{QL}};2]} + \left[\text{linguistic CI} \right]^{[\text{the manual to use Axioms 1 and 2}]} \text{ (in } \mathcal{A}_{\text{CW}^*}) \\ \approx \boxed{\text{Bayesian statistics}} \quad (5) \end{array} \right.$$

Only one measurement is allowed

where it suffices to consider that $\mathcal{A}_{\text{CC}^*} = C(\Theta)$ and $\mathcal{A}_{\text{CW}^*} = L^\infty(\Theta, \mu)$ (*cf.* refs. [17, 18]).

²There are various versions of the Copenhagen interpretation, but none of them convince me (*cf.* [8]). In QL, "Only one measurement is allowed" is the most important point, and I contend that this is the true Copenhagen interpretation. Furthermore, I contend that "Only one measurement is allowed" and "Kolmogorov's extension theorem" are the same statement (*cf.* ref.[12]). Also, note that von Neumann-Lüders projection postulate necessarily does not mean multiple measurements (*cf.* ref. [14]).

After all, we have the following classification:

$$\text{QL} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{commutative QL} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \boxed{\text{Commutative } C^*\text{-QL}} \left(\xleftarrow{\text{progress}} \text{Fisher statistics} \right) \\ \boxed{\text{Commutative } W^*\text{-QL}} \left(\xleftarrow{\text{progress}} \text{Bayesian statistics} \right) \end{array} \right. \quad (\text{cf. ref. [23]}) \\ \text{non-commutative QL: } W^*\text{-algebra } B(H); \text{ quantum mechanics (due to von Neumann)} \end{array} \right. \quad (6)$$

Here, the most important question in this paper is the following.

(A) What is the meaning of “ $\xleftarrow{\text{progress}}$ ” in (6)?

In this paper, I conclude that

(B) Commutative C^* -QL [resp. commutative W^* -QL] is the theoretical completion of Fisher statistics [resp. Bayesian statistics]. (For Commutative W^* -QL (Bayesian statistics), see ref.[23]).

Thus, in this paper I devote myself to Fisher statistics.

♠**Note 1.** (i): This paper positions Quantum Language (QL) as the natural successor to Fisher statistics, in the same way that von Neumann extended the mathematical formalism of quantum mechanics.

(ii): This paper also concerns the interpretation of quantum mechanics. The interpretation of quantum mechanics (=QM) is a matter of defining the manual to use Axioms^{QM} 1 and 2. In fact, there is no unique manual that can be determined. Therefore, the question arises as to which manual is superior, and this is the problem of interpreting quantum mechanics. There are the Copenhagen interpretation (and there are various versions of it), the Many-Worlds Interpretation, Bohmian Mechanics, QBism, etc. I think the interpretation problem is as follows (cf. ref. [12]) :

(#₁) QM, commutative QL, etc. are types of QL. Therefore, once the interpretation of QL is determined, the interpretation of QM, commutative QL, etc. is automatically determined.

Therefore, I propose the following interpretation of QL.

(#₂) **Only one measurement is allowed.**

which is henceforth called **the linguistic Copenhagen interpretation of QL**. This proposal (#₂) requires rigorous scrutiny, yet I regard it as the ‘true Copenhagen interpretation,’ chiefly for its simplicity and unifying power. The reason for this is its simplicity. That is, in my QL framework, measurement, picture (with no Schrödinger picture), and state updating (with no updating) can be handled in a unified and consistent manner (cf. Note 5 (iii)). Summing up, we say:

(#₃) The interpretation problem of quantum mechanics, from the standpoint of physics, should be left to future developments of quantum theory. In contrast, the interpretation of epistemological quantum language (QL) is fully determined by the principle that ‘(#₂): only one measurement is allowed’.

(iii): The principle (#₂) implies that the many-worlds interpretation (MWI, proposed by Hugh Everett III) is not valid, because we never observe any worlds beyond the first one.

2 Commutative C^* -QL (= $C(\Theta)$ -QL)

2.1 Introduction of the concept of observable (=NPOVMS (Normalized Positive Operator-Valued Measure Space)) to statistics

Please take a look at the epistemology section of Figure 1 (the area surrounded by the red dotted line). The goal of all of them (except mathematicians such as Boole and Cantor) was to discover what is “observable.” However, only von Neumann succeeded in this. QL simply imitated him. The reader will understand that discovering "observable (=NPOVMS, in short, POVM)" is as difficult as discovering operator algebra in mathematics, and our goal is to add the concept of "observable" to statistics^⑦.

A compact space Θ [resp. $\theta \in \Theta$] is called a *state space* [resp. *state*]. Put \mathcal{A}_{CC^*} (=commutative C^* algebra) = $C(\Theta) = \{f : \Theta \rightarrow \mathbb{C} \mid f \text{ is a complex valued continuous function on } \Theta\}$.

Definition 2.1. An *observable* $\mathcal{O} = (X, \mathcal{X}, E)$ in \mathcal{A}_{CC^*} (= $C(\Theta)$) is defined as follows (cf. ref. [5]):

- [Additivity] X is a set, \mathcal{X} is a σ -field of the power set 2^X (= $\mathcal{P}(X)$). E is a mapping from \mathcal{X} to $C(\Theta)$ satisfying:
 - (a) for every $\Xi \in \mathcal{X}$, $E(\Xi)$ is a non-negative element in $C(\Theta)$ such that $0 \leq E(\Xi) \leq I$,
 - (b) $E(\emptyset) = 0$ and $E(X) = I$, where 0 and I is the zero element 0 and the identity I in $C(\Theta)$ respectively.
 - (c) [σ -additivity]

$$\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} E(\Xi_i) = E\left(\bigcup_{i=1}^{\infty} \Xi_i\right) \quad (\text{in the sense of norm topology}) \quad (7)$$

for all $\Xi_1, \Xi_2, \dots \in \mathcal{X}$ such that $\Xi_i \cap \Xi_j = \emptyset$ (if $i \neq j$)

In the commutative case, an observable is similar to a Markov kernel $K(\theta, dy)$ from Θ to (X, \mathcal{X}) .³

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♠**Note 2.** When we write out the variables of E , we have

$$(X, \mathcal{X}, [E(\Xi)](\theta)) \quad (\Xi \in \mathcal{X}, \theta \in \Theta).$$

Therefore, by writing $(X, \mathcal{X}, [E(\cdot)](\theta))$, we may say that the observable $\mathcal{O} = (X, \mathcal{X}, E)$ is a probability space with parameter θ .

Example 2.2. [Observable in $C(\Theta)$].

Figure 2: Cold, Warm, Hot

³Here “kernel” is used in the measure-theoretic sense. It is a structural object; probabilities are obtained only after coupling it with a state via Axiom 1.

Read the following while looking at the figure above.

Put $\Theta = [0, 100](\equiv \{\theta \in \mathbb{R} \mid 0 \leq \theta \leq 100\})$, $\mathcal{A} = C(\Theta)$. Also, $\theta_0(\in \Theta)$ is regarded as a state.

Put $X = \{C, W, H\}$ and consider the observable $O = (X, 2^X, E)$, where $[E(\{x\})] : \Theta \rightarrow [0, 1](\subseteq \mathbb{R})$ is continuous ($\forall x \in X$), such that $0 \leq [E(\{x\})](\theta) \leq 1$ ($\forall x \in X, \theta \in \Theta$),

$$[E(\{C\})](\theta) + [E(\{W\})](\theta) + [E(\{H\})](\theta) = 1 \quad (\forall \theta \in \Theta) \quad (8)$$

2.2 Axiom^{CC*QL} 1 [Measurement] in (4)

With any (*classical*) system S , a commutative C^* -algebra $C(\Theta)$ can be associated in which the commutative C^* -QL (4) of that system can be formulated. A *state* of the system S is represented by an element $\theta(\in \Theta)$ and an *observable* is represented by an observable $O = (X, \mathcal{X}, E)$ in $C(\Theta)$. Fix a state $\theta_0(\in \Theta)$. The *measurement of the observable O for the system S with the state θ_0* is denoted by $M_{C(\Theta)}(O, S_{[\theta_0]})$ (or more precisely, $M_{C(\Theta)}(O = (X, \mathcal{X}, E), S_{[\theta_0]})$). An observer can obtain a measured value $x(\in X)$ by the measurement $M_{C(\Theta)}(O, S_{[\theta_0]})$.

The Axiom 1 presented below is a kind of mathematical generalization of Born's probabilistic interpretation of quantum mechanics (*cf.* formula (1)). And thus, it is no longer a law of physics, but an axiom of epistemology

Now we can present Axiom 1 as follows.

Axiom^{CC*QL} 1 [State, Measurement] in the commutative C^* -algebraic QL

- The probability that a measured value $x(\in X)$ belongs to $\Xi(\in \mathcal{X})$ is obtained by the measurement $M_{C(\Theta)}(O = (X, \mathcal{X}, E), S_{[\theta_0]})$ is given by $[E(\Xi)](\theta_0)$ ($=_{C(\Theta)^*} \langle \delta_{\theta_0}, E(\Xi) \rangle_{C(\Theta)}$), where δ_{θ_0} is the point measure at $\theta_0(\in \Theta)$.

Figure 3: Measurement

♠**Note 3.** (i): Putting $\mathbb{P}_\theta(\Xi) = [E(\Xi)](\theta)$, we have a probability space $(X, \mathcal{X}, \mathbb{P}_\theta)$ with a parameter $\theta(\in \Theta)$, which can be identified with an observable (X, \mathcal{X}, E) in $C(\Theta)$. Thus we can propose Axiomatic Fisher statistics:

Axiom^{FS} 1 (Probability): Consider a probability space $(X, \mathcal{X}, \mathbb{P}_\theta)$ with a parameter $\theta(\in \Theta)$. Assume that a parameter $\theta_0(\in \Theta)$ is fixed. Thus, we say:

- The probability that a sample taken from the probability space $(X, \mathcal{X}, \mathbb{P}_{\theta_0})$ belongs to $\Xi(\in \mathcal{X})$ is $\mathbb{P}_{\theta_0}(\Xi)$.

(ii): Axiom^{CC*QL} 1 and Axiom^{FS} 1 are very similar, and thus many readers might consider the two to be the same. The difference is that QL is built on $C(\Theta)$ (i.e., commutative C^* -algebra), on the other hand, Axiom^{FS} 1 is built on Θ , and thus, it is free for the mathematical structure of operator algebra. In other words, Axiom^{CC*QL} 1 and quantum mechanics must always be compared and considered. For example, the Heisenberg picture is represented in operator algebra, and thus, in statistics, the Schrödinger picture is not popular in spite that the Heisenberg picture is more essential than the Schrödinger picture.

Example 2.3. C^* -algebraic formulation, [Classical QL (= commutative QL)]

For simplicity, assume that $\Theta = [0, 100]$, and the observable is represented by $O = (X = \{C, W, H\}, 2^X, E)$ as in Example 2.2.

Figure 4: Drinking water

We have a measurement $M_{C(\Theta)}(O = (X = \{C, W, H\}, 2^X, E), S_{[\theta_0]})$. Thus, Axiom 1 says that

- (#₁) When an observer measures the observable $O = (X = \{C, W, H\}, 2^X, E)$ for a system S with the state $\theta_0(\in \Theta)$, the probability that a measured value $x(\in X)$ is obtained is given by $[E(\{x})](\theta_0)$.

Using everyday language, we say:

- (#₂) Suppose 100 subjects are asked to drink this glass of θ_0 °C water. One person is randomly selected from these 100 and asked, “Is this water cold, warm, hot?”

$$\text{The probability that this subject answers } \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{“it is cold”} \\ \text{“it is warm”} \\ \text{“it is hot”} \end{array} \right\} \text{ is } \left\{ \begin{array}{l} [E(\{C\})](\theta_0) \\ [E(\{W\})](\theta_0) \\ [E(\{H\})](\theta_0) \end{array} \right\}$$

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2.3 Bald man paradox (Sorites paradox)

Example 2.4 (Bald Man Paradox and Fuzzy Logic in the Statistical Framework *cf.* refs. [4, 15, 17, 18]). I would like to measure whether “Is Mr. X bald or not?”

Let M be the set of all males. Let $\Theta = [0, 1]$ be the state space consisting of the states of the heads of all adult males. That is, for any male $m(\in M)$, a state $\theta(m)(\in \Theta)$ is, for example, defined such as (9) below.

- Let us assume that the maximum number of hairs on an adult man’s head is 150,000 (i.e., 1.5×10^5). Let M be the set of all adult men. For each $m_i \in M$, define his **bald rate** $\theta(m_i)$ by

$$\theta(m_i) = \frac{\text{Number of hairs on } m_i\text{'s head}}{1.5 \times 10^5}. \quad (9)$$

Let $X = \{Y, N\}$ be a set of measured values. I would like to construct a measurement $M_{C(\Theta)}(\mathcal{O} = (X, 2^X, \mathbb{E}^{\text{bald}}), S_{[\theta(m)]})$. That is, it suffices to define \mathbb{E}^{bald} below.

Consider the observable

$$(X = \{Y, N\}, \mathcal{E}(= 2^X), \mathbb{E}^{\text{bald}}) \quad \text{in } C(\Theta(= [0, 1]))$$

where:

$$(\#) \text{ For every } \theta \in [0, 1], \text{ we have } \mathbb{E}_\theta^{\text{bald}}(\{Y\}) + \mathbb{E}_\theta^{\text{bald}}(\{N\}) = 1.$$

where

$$\mathbb{E}_\theta^{\text{bald}}(\{Y\}) = [\mathbb{E}^{\text{bald}}(\{Y\})](\theta), \quad \mathbb{E}_\theta^{\text{bald}}(\{N\}) = [\mathbb{E}^{\text{bald}}(\{N\})](\theta).$$

We define the probability measure $\mathbb{E}_\theta^{\text{bald}}$ as follows:

$$\mathbb{E}_\theta^{\text{bald}}(\{N\}) = \begin{cases} 0 & (0 \leq \theta \leq 0.3), \\ \frac{5}{2}\theta - \frac{3}{4} & (0.3 \leq \theta \leq 0.7), \\ 1 & (0.7 \leq \theta \leq 1.0), \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

$$\mathbb{E}_\theta^{\text{bald}}(\{Y\}) = 1 - \mathbb{E}_\theta^{\text{bald}}(\{N\}) \quad (0 \leq \theta \leq 1).$$

Figure 5: Observable $(X = \{Y, N\}, \mathcal{X} = 2^X, \mathbb{E}_\theta^{\text{bald}})_{\theta \in \Theta=[0,1]}$

Suppose we ask the following question to 100 respondents:

(b₁) Is Mr. m_i (with bald rate $\theta(m_i)$) bald?

Assume their answers are distributed as follows:

(b₂) $\begin{cases} \text{About } 100 \cdot \mathbb{E}_{\theta(m_i)}^{\text{bald}}(\{Y\}) \text{ respondents say "Yes" } \\ \text{About } 100 \cdot (1 - \mathbb{E}_{\theta(m_i)}^{\text{bald}}(\{Y\})) \text{ respondents say "No" } \end{cases}$

Figure 6: Without measurement, there is no probability

This can be interpreted probabilistically as follows:

(b₃) If one respondent is randomly selected from the 100, the probability that they answer “yes” is $p_1 = \mathbb{E}_{\theta(m_i)}^{\text{bald}}(\{Y\})$.

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♠**Note 4.** (i): The bald man (Sorites) paradox has been proven in ref [4] in engineering terms. However, for fuzzy logic to be accepted by many scientists and engineers, it must be justified within a theory that is more theoretically superior to statistics (or dynamical systems theory). I respect the position that there may be fuzzy concepts that cannot be reduced to probability. However, in that case, the verifiability of the framework as a scientific theory would be constrained.

(ii): Statistics is a theory that eliminates observables from quantum language. However, if we are allowed to identify Figure 5 (observable) with the following Figure 7 (probability space with a parameter θ), Commutative C^* -QL and Fisher statistics is not so different.

Figure 7: Probability space with a parameter θ

However, it should be noted that Figure 5 (\approx observable) is not related to probability, but Figure 7 is relate to probability. Again, see footnote³. For example, when considering Fisher ’ s maximum likelihood method, the concept of “likelihood” is derived from a probability space with a parameter θ . In the case of quantum language, however, the “observable” is given from the outset.

(iii): The table below represents “the progress of **metaphysics** (blue) and epistemology (black)”.(*cf.ref.* [19])

mind-matter dualism	A(= <u>mind</u>) [measurer, measured value]	B(body:between <u>A</u> and C) [observable (measuring instrument)]	C(= <u>matter</u>) [measuring object]
Plato(BC427-BC347) (Allegory of the sun)	actual world	(Idea, Sunlight)	Idea world
Aristotle (BC384-BC322)	×	×	<u>hyle</u> [eidos]
Descartes (1596-1650)	I, mind, brain	body	<u>matter</u>
Newton (1642-1727)	×	×	<u>particle</u> [position x , momentum p]
Locke (1632-1704)	mind	secondary quality	primary quality
Kant (1724-1804)	phenomenon	cognition	thing-in-itself
Statistics (Fisher) (1890 - 1962)	sample (measured value) [$x(\in X)$]	probability space <u>with a parameter</u> ⁴ [$(X, \mathcal{X}, P_\theta)$]	<u>system</u> [parameter $\theta(\in \Theta)$]
QM (\approx QL) von Neumann (1903-1957)	sample (measured value) [$x(\in X)$]	observable (= POVN) [(X, \mathcal{X}, E)]	<u>system</u> [state $ u\rangle\langle u , \theta$]

The important thing is the difference in the underlying mathematics.

(#₁) **metaphysics** [monism: matter]

Aristotle(no math) \rightarrow Newton (differential equation)

(#₂) epistemology [dualism: mind-body-matter]

Kant and earlier (no math) \rightarrow statistics (Kolmogorov probability theory) \rightarrow QL (operator algebra, von Neumann)

Thus, I think that the history of epistemology (in Figure 1) is the history of the search for POVM.

2.4 Axiom 2 [Causality]

Next, we explain Axiom 2. Let $(\mathbb{T}, t_0; \leq)$ be a tree-like semi-ordered set with the root t_0 . The following two are typical.

⁴The probability space with a parameter is not an observable. See (ii) in Note 4.

Figure 8: Tree-like semi-ordered set with the root t_0

Assume that, for each $t \in \mathbb{T}$, a C^* -algebra $C(\Theta_t)$ is associated.

Definition 2.5. [Markov operator, Markov map, homomorphism] A continuous linear operator $\Phi_{1,2} : C(\Theta_2) \rightarrow C(\Theta_1)$ is called a *Markov operator*, if it satisfied

$$(\#_1) \quad \Phi_{1,2}(L) \geq 0 \quad (\forall L \in C(\Theta_2) \text{ such that } L \geq 0)$$

$$(\#_2) \quad \Phi_{1,2}(I_2) = I_1, \text{ where } I_1 \text{ and } I_2 \text{ is identity maps in } C(\Theta_1) \text{ and } C(\Theta_2) \text{ respectively.}$$

The dual Markov operator $\Phi_{1,2}^* : C(\Theta_1)^* \rightarrow C(\Theta_2)^*$ is defined by the dual operator of Markov operator $\Phi_{1,2}$. Note that this is essentially the same as Markov map $\phi_{1,2} : \Theta_1 \rightarrow C(\Theta_2)^*$, since we have the identification: $\Theta_1 \ni \theta_1 \longleftrightarrow \delta_{\theta_1} \in C^*(\Theta_1)$. That is, the Markov operator [resp. Markov map] corresponds to the Heisenberg picture [resp. the Schrödinger picture].

Further, a Markov operator $\Phi_{1,2} : C(\Theta_2) \rightarrow C(\Theta_1)$ is called a *homomorphism*, if it satisfies tha

$$(\#_3) \quad \Phi_{1,2}(L_2 \cdot M_2) = \Phi_{1,2}(L_2)\Phi_{1,2}(M_2) \text{ and } \Phi_{1,2}(L_2^*) = (\Phi_{1,2}(L_2))^* \quad (\forall L_2, M_2 \in C(\Theta_2))$$

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A homomorphism $\Phi_{t_1,t_2} : C(\Theta_{t_2}) \rightarrow C(\Theta_{t_1})$ is characterized as follows:

(#4) there exists a continuous map $\phi_{t_1,t_2} : \Theta_{t_1} \rightarrow \Theta_{t_2}$ such that

$$[\Phi_{t_1,t_2}(g_{t_2})](\theta_{t_1}) = g_{t_2}(\phi_{t_1,t_2}(\theta_{t_1})) \quad (\forall \theta_{t_1} \in \Theta_{t_1}, \forall g_{t_2} \in C(\Theta_{t_2})), \quad (11)$$

where ϕ_{t_1,t_2} is called a causal map.

Figure 9: Causal map $\phi_{1,2}$ and causal operator $\Phi_{1,2}$

Now we can propose Axiom 2 (i.e., causality).

Here, the Heisenberg folding is given by

$$\widehat{E}(\Xi_0 \times \Xi_1 \times \Xi_2) = (E_0(\Xi_0)) \times \Phi_{01} \left(E_1(\Xi_1) \times (\Phi_{12} E_2(\Xi_2)) \right) \quad (15)$$

Here, ‘ \times ’ denotes pointwise multiplication in $C(\Theta_0)$ (and in $C(\Theta_1)$). Therefore, by performing the measurement $\mathbf{M}_{C(\Theta_0)}(\widehat{\mathcal{O}}(= (\widehat{X}, \widehat{\mathcal{X}}, \widehat{E}), S_{[\theta_0]}))$, we can conclude the following:

- In the measurement $\mathbf{M}_{C(\Theta_0)}(\widehat{\mathcal{O}}(= (\widehat{X}, \widehat{\mathcal{X}}, \widehat{E}), S_{[\theta_0]}))$, the probability that the measured value (x_0, x_1, x_2) belongs to $\Xi_0 \times \Xi_1 \times \Xi_2$ is given by $[\widehat{E}(\Xi_0 \times \Xi_1 \times \Xi_2)](\theta_0)$.

This truly embodies the “measure only once” philosophy (*cf.* Note 1).

♠**Note 5.** (i): In Bayesian statistics, the above method is more remarkable (*cf.* ref. [23]). Once observables are made explicit, any multi-time statistical inference boils down to a **single Heisenberg folding followed by a single Bayesian update**. The same syntax works in both the classical (commutative) and quantum (non-commutative) cases — and providing exactly that minimal machinery is what Quantum Language (QL) is about. That is, we can characterize Kalman filter as follows.

$$\boxed{\text{Kalman filter}} = \boxed{\text{Bayesian method}} + \boxed{\text{Heisenberg folding}} \quad (\text{cf. ref. [23]}) \quad (16)$$

It should be noted that this beautiful assertion cannot be obtained without introducing observables into statistics.

However, in the case of statistics, which does not have the concept of observable, it is not as simple as shown below.

♠**Note 6.** (i): Putting $\mathbb{P}_\theta(\Xi) = [E(\Xi)](\theta)$, we have a probability space $(X, \mathcal{X}, \mathbb{P}_\theta)$ with a parameter $\theta(\in \Theta)$, which can be identified with an observable (X, \mathcal{X}, E) in $C(\Theta)$. Thus we can propose ‘causality’ in Axiomatic Fisher statistics:

Axiom^{FS} 2 (Causality): Consider parameter spaces (= state spaces) Θ_{t_1} and Θ_{t_2} .
 (b): Causality is represented by the dual Markov operator $\Phi_{t_1, t_2}^* : C(\Theta_{t_1})^* \rightarrow C(\Theta_{t_2})^*$

(ii) [Schrödinger picture]: Consider Example 2.6 in the context of Fisher statistics (Axiom^{FS} 2). Thus,

$$\bullet t_0 \longrightarrow \bullet t_1 \longrightarrow \bullet t_2 \quad (17)$$

Therefore, (using equation (14) as a hint) we obtain the following:

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{O}_0 = (X_0, \mathcal{X}_0, E_0) \\ \bullet : C(\Theta_{t_0}) \\ \parallel \\ \bullet : C(\Theta_{t_0})^* \\ E_0(\Xi_0)\rho_0 \end{array} \xrightarrow{\Phi_{01}^*} \begin{array}{c} \bullet : C(\Theta_{t_1})^* \\ E_1(\Xi_1)(\Phi_{01}^* E_0(\Xi_0)\rho_0) \end{array} \xrightarrow{\Phi_{12}^*} \begin{array}{c} \bullet : C(\Theta_{t_2})^* \\ E_2(\Xi_2)(\Phi_{12}^*(E_1(\Xi_1)(\Phi_{01}^* E_0(\Xi_0)\rho_0))) \end{array} \quad (18)$$

However, in Fisher statistics the concept of an observable does not exist; hence, the terms $E_0(\Xi_0)$, $E_1(\Xi_1)$, and $E_2(\Xi_2)$ above cannot be used. Therefore, we replace them with $\chi_{\Xi'_0}$, $\chi_{\Xi'_1}$, $\chi_{\Xi'_2}$ (where $\Xi'_0 \subseteq X_0$, $\Xi'_1 \subseteq X_1$, $\Xi'_2 \subseteq X_2$) to obtain: ⁶

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{O}_0=(X_0, X_0, E_0) \\
\bullet: C(\Theta_{t_0}) \\
\parallel \\
\bullet: C(\Theta_{t_0})^* \xrightarrow{\chi_{\Xi'_0} \rho_0} \xrightarrow{\Phi_{01}^*} \bullet: C(\Theta_{t_1})^* \xrightarrow{\chi_{\Xi'_1} (\Phi_{01}^* \chi_{\Xi'_0} \rho_0)} \xrightarrow{\Phi_{12}^*} \bullet: C(\Theta_{t_2})^* \xrightarrow{\chi_{\Xi'_2} (\Phi_{12}^* (\chi_{\Xi'_1} (\Phi_{01}^* \chi_{\Xi'_0} \rho_0)))}
\end{array} \tag{19}$$

(iii): Axiom^{CC*QL} 1 and Axiom^{FS} 1 (in Note 3) are very similar, and thus many readers might consider the two to be the same. The difference is that QL is built on $C(\Theta)$ (i.e., commutative C^* -algebra), on the other hand, Axiom^{FS} 1 is built on Θ , and thus, it is free for the mathematical structure of operator algebra. In other words, Axiom^{CC*QL} 1 and quantum mechanics must always be compared and considered. From the standpoint of the insights of quantum mechanics, the Heisenberg picture is the formal one, whereas the Schrödinger picture is a “method for special cases.”

♠**Note 7. (i) QBism:** Both QL and QBism (ref. [9]) are applicable to both classical and quantum systems. In this sense, they are similar. However, QL is “Heisenberg picture first,” while QBism is “Schrödinger picture first.” Thus, the formula (19) with a mixed state ρ_0 is essential to QBism and not adopted in QL’s picture-neutral presentation. While it would be good for the two to have a mutually respectful relationship, they may be destined to reach a conclusion someday. In this case, I think QL will argue for the convenience of formula (16).

(ii)**Categorical quantum mechanics (e.g., [10]):** CQM is a diagrammatic formalism (language) for the computation, design, and verification of quantum processes; it is not quantum mechanics itself. Accordingly, if one’s sole aim is to produce numerical predictions, QL as a computational OS suffices. By contrast, for the design, verification, and optimization of large-scale protocols, CQM functions extremely effectively as a front-end basis for type checking, causal-consistency checks, and automated simplification.

Among the familiar interpretations of quantum mechanics—Copenhagen, many-worlds, QBism, and others—I regard QL’s linguistic Copenhagen interpretation (“Only one measurement is allowed”) as the most concise and practically powerful.⁷ From this standpoint, I hope researchers in CQM will also take an interest in QL, since it allows both statistics in the commutative slice and standard quantum theory in the noncommutative slice to be treated within a single “language of measurement.”

⁶Here, $\chi_{\Xi'_1}(\theta_1) = 1$ (if $\theta_1 \in \Xi'_1$), $= 0$ (otherwise).

⁷I believe that there is no best answer to the “problem of interpreting quantum mechanics,” but there is a best answer to the “problem of interpreting quantum language.”

3 Metaphysics (Newton, Einstein) vs. Epistemology (Fisher, von Neumann, QL)

In previous section, we studied Commutative $C^* - QL$ as follows:

$$\boxed{\text{Commutative } C^*\text{-QL}} = \overset{[\text{Axiom}^{CC^*QL} 1]}{\boxed{\text{measurement (observable)}}} + \overset{[\text{Axiom}^{CC^*QL};2]}{\boxed{\text{causal relation}}} + \overset{[\text{the manual to use Axioms}^{QL} 1 \text{ and } 2]}{\boxed{\text{linguistic CI}}} \quad (\text{in } \mathcal{A}_{CC^*})$$

(20(=(4)))

Heisenberg picture Only one measurement is allowed

And, Fisher statistics is as follows:

$$\boxed{\text{Fisher statistics}} = \overset{[\text{Axiom}^{FS} 1] \text{ in Note 3}}{\boxed{\text{probability space with parameter}}} + \overset{[\text{Axiom}^{FS} 2] \text{ in Note 5}}{\boxed{\text{causal relation}}} + \overset{[\text{the manual to use Axioms}^{FS} 1 \text{ and } 2]}{\boxed{\text{Various methods}}}$$

(21)

Schrödinger picture Kolmogorov extension theory (?)

However, as already noted in Note 4 (ii), an observable and a probability space with parameter are closely related; roughly speaking, one could almost regard them as “the same.”

For more than a century since Fisher, work has been carried out using probability spaces with a parameter. It is natural to suppose that, had substantial inconveniences been strongly felt, the notion of an observable would have been introduced earlier. In other words, from the standpoint that regards statistics simply as a branch of applied mathematics, the weaknesses of Fisherian statistics is unlikely to become apparent.

The difference, I believe, lies not in technical matters, but rather in considerations of aesthetic or philosophical nature.

Comparing Fisher statistics with commutative C^* -QL, we can state the following:

- Fisher statistics is QL with the use of the operator algebra $C(\Theta)$ prohibited.

For example, in Fisher statistics the following holds:

- Since an “observable” is defined within $C(\Theta)$, Fisher statistics does not use “observables” but instead employs a “probability space with parameter.”
- The Heisenberg picture is a theory formulated within $C(\Theta)$; therefore, Fisher statistics uses the Schrödinger picture, which is a theory formulated within Θ (or, $\mathcal{M}(\Theta)(= C(\Theta)^*)$).

and related aspects.

Although Fisher (and the statisticians of his time) were sufficiently familiar with results such as the Riesz representation theorem, they did not construct a statistics centered on $C(\Theta)$. This was likely because a wealth of substantial results could be produced using only a “probability space with parameter.” For Fisher, statistics was “a logical system linking observation and inference (= epistemology),” and it was probably not his intention for it to be regarded merely as applied mathematics. Simply “considering a problem by means of a probability space with parameter” was sufficient, and it was natural that the methodology would differ from problem to problem; however, this eventually developed into the Fisher vs. Neyman–Pearson controversy. The mathematically oriented understanding, symbolized by Kolmogorov’s probability theory, also entered statistics, and the resulting confusion in the history of statistics closely resembles the confusion in the history of epistemology (Figure 1 and Note 4(iii)).

Remark 3.1. Now, our aim has been to answer the question, “What is Fisher statistics?” This is, in fact, an open question, and our answer is as follows:

(C) Rather than (21), the correct answer is (20).

Of course, it is possible to defend the standpoint of (21) to some extent, but there are certain inconveniences in doing so. In that approach, the question “What is Bayesian statistics?” inevitably arises, and answering in the manner of (21) only increases the ambiguity. Our answer has already been stated in (6), namely:

$$\text{QL} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{commutative QL} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \boxed{\text{Commutative } C^*\text{-QL}} \left(\xleftarrow{\text{progress}} \text{Fisher statistics} \right) \\ \boxed{\text{Commutative } W^*\text{-QL}} \left(\xleftarrow{\text{progress}} \text{Bayesian statistics} \right) \text{ cf. ref. [23]} \quad (22(=6)) \end{array} \right. \\ \text{non-commutative QL: } W^*\text{-algebra } B(H); \text{ quantum mechanics (due to von Neumann)} \end{array} \right.$$

In metaphysics (Newtonian mechanics, relativity theory), it suffices to focus solely on describing the world accurately: the world precedes the mathematics. In epistemology, such as statistics, however, the concern is not to “describe the world accurately” but to first decide on the “framework in which the world is to be described.” One must first fix the mathematics—in this case, an operator algebra. Kolmogorov, likewise, sought to begin from mathematics (probability theory \approx measure theory), and this was a great success; yet, because no topological or algebraic structure was given in advance, relations such as observation and causality were not visible. Our proposal (and von Neumann’s) is to start from an operator algebra, and within it, to formulate observation, causality, and probability. ////

However, everyone acknowledges that Fisher’s achievements are among the greatest of the twentieth century, and of course I agree. The author is convinced of the following:

$$(G) \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{metaphysics: Newton, Einstein} \quad \quad \quad (\text{formulated in differential geometry}) \\ \text{epistemology: Fisher, von Neumann, QL} \quad (\text{formulated in operator algebra}) \end{array} \right.$$

Research in and around epistemology is a field full of misleading labyrinths, and one must proceed while keeping firmly in mind the structure (G) (and Figure 1). I do not dispute the value of various schools of thought, but I believe one should proceed only after understanding that Figure 1 is fundamental. I contend that the dissemination of this structure to the wider community is one of the most important matters in modern science.

Acknowledgements: I’m always grateful for the support of ChatGPT. In a few years, humans will no longer be able to surpass AI even in the field of quantum mechanics. However, I hope that future AI will recognize that it was humans who first reached the pinnacle of the most traditional academic field, epistemology (i.e., true statistics).

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